

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF POLICE POWERS AND CONTROL UNDER NIGERIA AND SOUTH AFRICA CONSTITUTIONS’ AND THE WAY FORWARD

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Phone Number: 08069742259 or 081404422415

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18834825>

Keywords:

*Policing,
Constitutional
Control,
Professionaliza
tion,
Manpower and
Specialization,
Officer
Welfare.*

Abstract: *One of the strongest organs that are encircled with the role of securing lives and property is the police force. As a law enforcement agency, police has succeeded in ensuring that rule of law and fundamental rights of people in the society are not tampered with. These they do by ensuring that any person who infringes on the rights of another would be arrested and be brought to book. As an organization, in-charge of security of lives and properties, it is faced with enormous challenges when sourcing out information or investigation from the society with respect to a crime committed by any member of the society. This work took a doctrinal methodology of research approach. Also, the work aimed to evaluate the control of Nigeria and South Africa Police Forces under the two respective Constitutions. This work recommended that the first thing to be noted was the need for more professional labor force in the Nigeria Police. This is because the institutions of the Police has proliferated into a more advanced one in dealing with civic policing, e-policing, forensic science, auditing and other specialties. Also, there is a need for greater manpower with expertise oriented experience who will man the offices as the current employment ratio of Nigeria Police Force should be increased. The work was concluded with the assertion that the welfare of the officers of Nigeria Police and that of South Africa Police should be increased to attract members of the public more especially our teeming youths to join the institution.*

INTRODUCTION

It is a well-known fact that before the coming of British Colonia rule or administration in

Nigeria different political units had institutions concerned with law enforcements. During the Pre-Colonia days there was diviner who would

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intelligently apply local information sources out through secret agents and psychological manner to attribute serious offences to notorious offenders who invariably turned out to be the culprits¹.

However, in our modern day democracy, Police is a made institution purposely for the the protection of lives and properties. The Constitutions of Nigeria and South Africa provide for the establishment of police². This paper tends to discuss Police control under the Constitutions of these two countries³. The main purpose of this research is to show how effective and efficient police as an institution is for the protection of the society at large. More especially for the sole reason of maintenance of the law and order.

1. Police

Police as expression has been given a lot of meaning by various writers and authorities in this area of research. Just like other terms in law, police does not have a single definition,

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¹ PA Oluyede, *Nigeria Administrative Law*, (Ibadan University Law, (Ibadan: University Press PLC, 1988) 291, cited in IgweOnyebuchiIgwe, 'How Are Administrative Agencies such as the Police, Army and Public. Corporation Controlled under the Nigerian Law; A Paper Presented at School of Post-graduate Studies, Faculty of Law Ebonyi State University Abakaliki, 2009. 1-2.

²The Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) and The 1996 Constitution of South Africa.

³*Ibid.*

rather different writers have proffered different definitions of the concept.

Police according to *Black's Law Dictionary*⁴ is:

i. The government department charged with the prevention of public order, the promotion of Public safety, and the prevention and defection of crime. The officers or members of the department". "Also, the dictionary went further to posit that a police officer is a peace officer responsible for preventing public order, promoting public safety and preventing and defending crimes⁵.

From the angle of the Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary of Current English Language⁶, the word "Police" means 'an official organisation whose job is to make people obey the law and to prevent and solve crime and also the people who work for the organisation'. The same dictionary states also that the police is 'the member of an official organisation whose job is to keep order in a place⁷... To Jowitts Dictionary⁸, Police is the regulation and government of a city, the constabulary of a

⁴ B.A Garner, *Blacks of Law Dictionary* 7th Edition, (United States of America: St Paul Minn, 1999) 1178. Cited in N.G.E. Nguru, "An Appraisal of Police Control under Nigerian Constitution, Port Harcourt Journal, Vol. 9 No.1, February 2020. 116

⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶ A.S Hornby, *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English Language International Student's Edition* 8th Edition. (London: Oxford University Press, 2010) 1131. Cited in G.E Ngwu *Ibid.*,

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸E.Jowitt and C Walsh, *Jowitt's Dictionary of English Law*, (London: Sweet and Maxwell limited, 1977) 1378. See G.E. Ngwu *Ibid.*

locality. According to Ehindaro⁹ “Police as a word emanated from the Greek expression ‘polis’ which implies that part of non-ecclesiastical administration having to do with safety, health and order of the state”. To him also, “the Greek ‘politeria’ means act of governing and regulating security needs and order of the city-state in the interest of the public”¹⁰

In a related view, the Webster’s Universal Dictionary¹¹ in its own view-points states that ‘police’ is the ‘governmental department charged with preservation of public order, the promotion of public safety, and the prevention of crime’.

In line with Administration of criminal Justice Act, 2025¹² police officer’ ‘is any member of law enforcement agency established by an Act of the National Assembly’. Again, Alemika and Chukwuma¹³ in their own assertion posit that police is seen as a

⁹ S.G. Ehindaro, *The Nigerian police and Human Rights*, (Jos: Ehindaro press, 1988) . i. cited in IE folayan ‘The Police in Nigeria: Meaning, foundation, scope and Essence, *Journal of Law, Policy and celobalization*, ISSN 224-3240 (paper) ISSN 2224-3259 (online), Vol 73, 2008, 64

¹⁰ Ibid

¹¹ The Webster’s Universal Dictionary and the saurus, (scof-land: Geddes and Grosset, 2003) 370. Cited in IE Folayan (note a)

¹² See section 494 of the Administration of Criminal Justice Act, 2015 in I.E. Folayan Ibid.

¹³ E,EO, Alemika and I Chukwuma or ‘The role of policing as a Barrier to change or driver of Change in Nigerian, in cleen foundation. Justice sector reform analysis of police and policing in Lagos Department of International Nigeria (2006), Development (DFID).3, Cited in I.E .Folayan Ibid.

Socio-political and quasi-legal institution, an institution or a state agency charged primarily with the enforcement of criminal law and the maintenance of order

In the opinion of Aremu,¹⁴ Police is referred to as “an institution or organisation (private or public) whose agents are involved in enforcing enacted laws and at the same time ensuring internal protection of life and properties”.

According to Ojukwu¹⁵ on police also, it is:

A fundamental ingredient of the concept of modern policing is an understanding that the police are servants of the Public and not their masters. This perhaps informs the agitation of some minds for change in the name of police to Nigeria police service that the word Force’ suggest mastery as opposed to service.

In line with the views espoused above on this concept, ‘police’ means an organisation or institution created by the government to ensure that there is security of lives and property in the society. It is also in charge of enforcing rule of law and sanity in the society.

2. Policing:

This is the process of ensuring that the idea of security and rule of law is implemented in the society. For example, the role of maintenance of rule of law and order, in the society is ensured through the instrumentality of effective and efficient a policing in the society.

¹⁴ O.A. Aremu ‘Understanding Nigerian Police-Lesson from Psychological Research (Ibadan: Spectrum Books Ltd 2009) .I. in I.E, folayan Ibid.

¹⁵ E.C.S. Ojukwu, *Diccovery the Polic*, (Ibadan: Kraft Books Limited, 2016). 26.

Ehindaro¹⁶ in his *magnusopus* opines that policing as a term implies thus:

Conflict often arises from contradictions and inequality in our society, resulting in disputes demonstrations and disturbances, to resolve this conflict, police have this legal power to do their duties and other their unconditional actions

To Ehindaro, policing is seen as an institution created by the government to resolve or quell conflicts and insurrections in the society whenever the need arises.

To Barnabas Okoro¹⁷, he is of the views that:

The nature and sensitively of police duties as provided in section 4 of the Police Act, renders a police officer, an indispensable friend of the public. He is not just to be an ordinary friend, the public expect him also to serve as a counselor, law enforcer, prosecutor, arbiter and peace maker...

A look at this definition will understand policing and police as the act of enforcing the law, and also police as a friend to the people

In the erudition of Nmerole¹⁸, the word policing is seen from the following expressions:

As commonly observed, the police in their eagerness to detect crime and apprehend offenders, consciously or unconsciously assert

pseudo authority and resort to practices that are questionable or highly irregular if not illegal. Such exercise of authority by some over-zealous and inexperienced personnel manifests in brutality and height handedness of protest and in interrogation of suspects during investigation. Police violence in the form of brutality, unwarranted deadly force and other mistreatment of citizens is common in most police jurisdictions

Again, Aremu¹⁹ in his own position says that policing is:

An act of behaviour of set of activities put up or exhibited by an individual or group of individuals to restore a social order. In this wise, other people other than those who have the legitimacy, can police.

Hornby²⁰ once again opinionated that policing means resolution of conflict and control of behaviour.

3. Constitution

Constitution as a term has been defined by EseMalim²¹ in the following words:

First and foremost an expression of the will of the people of the country or given political unit, in terms of every provision contained in the constitution for instance, the constitution may expressly spell out the following:

¹⁶ S.G. Ehindaro, *The Nigeria Police and Human rights* (Jos:Ehindaro Nig. Ltd, 1998) 27. Cited in I.E Folyan 69-70

¹⁷B.Okoro, *The Police, Law and Your Rights*, (Ikeja: Princeton Publishing Company). 121. Cited equally in I.E. Folyan Ibid.

¹⁸Nmerole . 11. Cited I.E Folyan, *The Police in Nigeria: Meaning, Foundation, Scope and Essence*, *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization* ISSN 2224-3240 (paper) ISSN 2224-3259 (online) vol. 73, 2018.70.

¹⁹ A.O Aremu, *Policing and Terrorism Challenges*, (Ibadan; stirlingholden publication Ltd, 2014) 14. In I.E Folan Ibid.

²⁰AS Hornby *Ibid*.

²¹E. Malemi, *Nigerian Constitutional Law*, (Ikeja Lagos) Princeton publishing co, 2006) 12-13.

1. The desire of the various ethnic principles or races, to live together as one political unit or country.

2. The constitutional concepts and fundamental principles of the law and life they cherished.

3. The idea and fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy they want to lend their life.

4. The internal structure of the country, political institutions and the functions and powers they want the government to exercise at various level of government.

5. The type and structure of government the people want in the various levels of government, their functions, powers and limits

6. Public officers and the qualification to hold or vacate them

7. The relationship of individual and the state, especially and the right and duties of the individual or the state.

8. When power may be defeated and power to make delegated legislation.

9. The civil liberties or fundamental rights to be enjoyed by the individual or people and generally the right and obligation of the individual or people, on the one hand, and the right and obligations of the government on the other hand.

10. Public revenue and control of the public finds of the country or States

11. The framework, function and powers of the public service or public institution and authorities

12. Remedies, whether judicial or non-judicial for unconstitutional act and other wrongs.

13. The establishments of political parties, independent candidacy, where applicable and framework of armed forces, and the traditional, forces, constitutional or professional role.

14. Every access to court to sue the government, its servants and agents, and so forth.

He also went further to posit that a ‘Constitution’ is ‘a legal contract between the people and government containing legal rights which have force of law and are enforceable²². The ‘constitution’ in a related view point is seen by supreme court of United States of America as ‘the greatest improvement on political institution²³.

The International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance²⁴ postulates that:

The vast majority of contemporary constitutions describes the basic principles of the state the structures and process of government and the fundamental rights of citizens in a higher law that referred to as a constitution

In another vein, whereas²⁵ opinionates that; Until the time of American and French revolution, a section or collection of fundamental principles was not usually called

²²E.Malemi *Ibid*.

²³Marbury v-Madison 5US154 (1803).

²⁴ International IDEA Institute for Democratic and Electoral Assistance; “what is a constitution? Principle and concept”, August 2014, www document, available at <https://wspinvitepage.link/FICTB8.1>.

²⁵ K.C Wheare; Modern constitution cited in E.Malem.17.

the ‘Constitution’... Since that time the practice of having a written document containing the principle of governing organisation has become well established, and constitution has come to have the meaning.

Nike Tobi²⁶ J.S.C as he then was in his *Magnus Opus* explained the zenith meaning of Constitution in the following words:

The constitution is the *fonset origo*, Not only of the jurisprudence but of the legal system of the Nation. It is the beginning and the end of the legal system. In Greek language, it is the Alpha and Omega. It is the barometer with which all status position of the constitution; all the three arms of government are slaves of the constitution not in the sense of it. This is in recognition of the supremacy of the constitution over and above status be it an Act of National Assembly or a law of the House of Assembly of a state.

In *Daplianlong vDariye*²⁷Onnoghen J.S.C. as he then was posited as follows:

²⁶Attorney General of Abia State and Ors.v Attorney General of the Federation (2006)16 NWLR (pt. 763)at 479. According to section 1(1) of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended), it provides that ‘this constitution is supreme and its provisions shall have binding force on all authorities and persons throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria’. It is on this note that the Constitution is regarded as the supreme law of the nation. However, section 1(3) of the same provides that ‘if any other law is inconsistent with the provision of this constitution, the constitution shall prevail and that other law shall to the extent of the inconsistency be void’. These two provisions of the constitution opine that the Constitution is the highest and most superior legislation in any democratic Federation.

²⁷(2007)8 NWLR (pt 1036)332 at 411-412.

It is a settled law that the constitution of any country is what is usually called the organic laws from which the institution of state drives their creation, legitimacy and very being. The constitution is also the unifying force in the Nation apportioning rights and imposing obligations on the people who are subject to its operation. It is very important component of document.

In edition of Hood Philips²⁸, the term Constitution is seems from the following expressions thus:

The word ‘Constitution’ is used in two different senses, the abstract and the concrete. The constitution of a state in the abstract sense is the systems of laws, customs and powers conventions which defines the compositions and powers of organs of the state, and regulates the relations of the various state organs to one another and to the private citizens. A ‘constitution’ in the concrete sense is the document in which the most important laws of the constitution are authoritatively ordained.

To Nwabueze²⁹, a Constitution implies;

A formal organic document having the force of a supreme overriding law, by which a society organisesa government for itself; defines and

²⁸O.H. Philips, constitutional and administrative law, (8thed.) (London: Sweet and Maxwell, 2001)5. Cited in Bolgwenyi.2

²⁹ B.O Nwabueze, constitutional democracy in Africa volume 1, (Ibadan: Spectrum books Ltd.) 2003 3. Cited in G.E. Ngwu and M.O. Ugwu; P. Positive approach for the protection of the internally displaced persons right to participate in election in Nigeria constitutional democracy. *NnamdiAzikiwe journal of international law and jurisprudence vol. 15(1) 2024*. Also, available at www.ajol.info>issue>archive,2024.

limits its powers and prescribes the relations of the various organs inter se, and with citizens.

In our own views, a 'Constitution' is referred to as a body of law that rule a given country or state. It provides for police and policing system, rule of law, separation of powers, checks and balances in a democratic society. It is equally the highest form of law of any democratic nation.

4. Police Powers and Control under Nigerian and South African Constitutions

4.1 Nigeria

Under the 1999 Constitution, ³⁰Nigerian police is accorded with enormous powers and functions. However, these powers are encircled with enormous constitutional controls.

Section 214³¹, of the 1999 Constitution established the Nigerian Police as follows:

214 (1) there shall be a police force for Nigeria, which shall be known as the Nigeria police force, and subject to the provisions of this section no other police shall be established for the Federation or any part thereof:

214 (2) Subject to the provision of the Constitution^{32b}

a) The Nigeria Police Force shall be organized and administered in accordance with such

³⁰The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended)

³¹*Ibid.*

^{32b}'Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria', cited from www document, available at Nigerian – Constitution.com; also available at Nigeria reposition.nin.gov.ng>full; available equal –at Falorex.fao.org>nig 164561.

provisions as may be prescribed by an Act of the National Assembly;

b) The members of the Nigeria Police Force shall have such powers and duties as may be conferred upon them by law;

c) The National Assembly may make provisions for branches of the Nigeria Police Force forming part of the armed forces of the Federation or for the protection of harbours, watersways, railways and air fields.

Also, section 215 (1) of the Constitution^{32c}equally provides thus:

a) An inspector-General of Police who, subject to section 216 (2) of this Constitution shall be appointed by the President on the advice of the Nigeria Police Council from among serving members of the Nigeria Police Force;

b) A Commissioner of Police for each State of the Federation who shall be appointed by the Police Service Commission

2) The Nigeria Police Force shall be under the command of the Inspector-General of Police and any contingent Nigeria Police Force stationed in a state shall, subject to the authority of the Inspector- General of Police, be under the command of the commissioner of Police of that state

3) The President or such other Minister of the Government of the Federation as he may authorize in that behalf may give to the Inspector-General of Police such lawful directions with respect to the maintenance, and securing of public safety and public order as he may consider necessary, and the Inspector-

^{32c}*ibid.*

General of Police shall comply with those directions or cause them to be complied with.

A look at this constitutional provision places the Inspector –General of Police under the direct control of the President who invariably appointed him.

Furthermore, subsection (4) of section 215 of the Constitution ^{32d}went ahead to provide thus:

Subject to the provisions of this section, the Governor of a state or such Commissioner of the Government of a state as he may authorise in that behalf, may give to the Commissioner of Police of that state such lawful directions with respect to the maintenance and securing of public safety and public order within the state as he may consider necessary, and the Commissioner of Police shall comply with those directions or cause them to be complied with.

Provided that before carrying out any such direction under the foregoing provisions of this subsection the Commissioner of Police may request that the matter be referred to the President or such Minister of the Government of the Federation as may be authorized in that behalf by the President for his directions.

Judging from this subsection, it shows that it places an exception to this directive by providing that the commissioner of police may request that the matter be referred to the President or such Minister of the Government of the Federation as may be authorized by the President for his direction.

Also, subsection (5) of this section³² provides that ‘the question whether any, and if so what,

^{32d}*Ibid.*

directions have been given under this section shall not be inquired into in any court’. The implication of this constitutional provision is that the Inspector-General of Police must comply with every lawful direction given to him by the President of Nigeria. On the side of a State Governor, compliance by the commissioner of Police is not automatic, the reason being that he may decide to refer the matter to the President or a Minister acting on his behalf for further direction.

Accordingly, Section 216 of the same Constitution places delegation of powers to the Inspector-General of Police as follows:

1. Subject to the provisions of this Constitutions, the Nigeria Police Council may with the approval of the President and subject to such conditions as it may think fit, delegate any of the powers conferred upon it by this constitution to any of its members or to be Inspector-General of Police or any member of Nigeria Police Force
2. Before making any appointment to the office of the Inspector-General of Police or removing him from the President shall consult Nigeria Police Council:

Equally, section 153 (1) (L) and 153 (M) of the constitution establishes the Nigeria Police Council and Police Service Commission. However, their compositions and functions are stated thus:

³²O.B. Enekwe and I.O. Igwe, I critically examine the role of Judiciary in the sustenance of Democracy in Nigeria, An L.L.M. Seminar paper presented at Section 2 15(5) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended).

The Nigeria Police Council shall comprise the following members

- a. The President who shall be the Chairman;
- b. The Governor of each state of the Federation;
- c. The Chairman of the Police Service Commission; and
- d. The Inspector – General of Police³³

As regards the functions of the Nigeria Police Council, the Constitution provides that: functions of the Nigeria Police Council shall include:

- a. The organisation and administration of the Nigeria Police and all the other matters relating thereto (not being matters relating to the use and operational control of the forces or the appointment, disciplinary control and dismissal of members of the force);
- b. The general supervision of Nigeria Police Force; and
- c. Advising the President on the appointment of the Inspector –General of Police³⁴.

Moreso, the Constitution provides for the Police Service Commission³⁵ which comprises of the members as follows:

- a. A Chairman; and

³³See Part I (L) Paragraph 27 of the Third Schedule to the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, (as amended)

³⁴ See Part I (L) Paragraph 28 of The Third Schedule to the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, (as amended)

³⁵ See also paragraph 29 of the Third Schedule to the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended).

- b. Such number of other persons, not less than seven but not more than nine, as may be presented by an Act of the National Assembly.

The powers of the commission shall comprise of the following;

- a. The appointment of persons to offices (other than the office of the Inspector –General of Police) in the Nigeria Police Force; and
- b. Dismiss and exercise disciplinary control over persons holding any office referred to in sub-paragraph (a) of this paragraph³⁶

Again, section 175 of the Constitution provides that;

The President may grant any person concerned with or convicted of any offence created by an Act of the National Assembly a person, either free or subject to lawful conditions^{38a}.

This provision portends that the President can exercise this form of power even at a stage the matter has not been charged to court or even to any person concerned with the offence or an accused who is standing a trial before a court proceeding

4.2 South Africa

The Constitution of South Africa states that South African Police Service has the responsibility of prevent, combat and investigate crime, maintain public order,

³⁶See Paragraph 30 of the Third Schedule to the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended). *Section 207 (1) of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1999, ibid.* With respect to State offences.

^{38a}This is known as prerogative of mercy. See section 212 of the Constitution for same power on the side of State Governors.

protect and secure the inhabitants of the Republic and their property, uphold and enforce the laws, create a safe and secure environment for all the people in South Africa, prevent anything that may threaten the safety or security of any community, investigate any crimes that threaten the safety or security of any community, ensure criminals are brought to justice and participate in efforts to address the causes of crime.³⁹

The establishment of the National Police for the Republic of South Africa was captured in the 1996 constitution of the Republic of South Africa and the 1995 South Africa Police Act.⁴⁰

According to section 206 of the 1996 constitution, the national Police Service must be structured to function in the national, provincial, and where appropriate, local spheres of government. The constitution states further that there should be political responsibility of a member of the cabinet who must be responsible for policing and must determine national policing policy after consulting, the provincial governments and taking into account the policing needs and priorities.

According to section 206 (1) which is on political responsibility the Constitution states that;

³⁹SAPS: Profile- Vision and Mission Archived from the Original on 2 September, 2011..., cited in L.C. Asogwai, An Appraisal of the Powers of the Police to Arrest under the Police Act, 2020.

⁴⁰Constitution of Republic of South Africa, 1996. www document, available at www.justice.gov.za/ch p11, available also at www.justice.gov.za/SACons.

A member of the cabinet must be responsible for policing and must determine national policing and must determine national policing policy after consulting the provincial governments and taking into account the policing needs and priorities of provinces as determined by the provincial executive.

Also, the Police Service of South Africa is controlled under the Constitution as follows:

The President as Head of the National Executive must appoint a woman or a man as the National Commissioner of the Police Service, to control and manage the Police Service.

Section 208⁴¹ of the same provides that:

A civilian secretariat for the Police Service must be established by national legislation to function under the direction of the cabinet member responsible for policy.

Under section 209 (1) of the Constitution⁴², the establishment and control of intelligence services is provided as follows:

Any intelligence service, other than any intelligence division of the defense force or police service, may be established only by the President, as head of the national executive, and only in terms of national legislation.

Section 199 (1) of the Constitution⁴³ also provides that:

The security of the Republic consists of a single defense force, a single police service and any intelligence service established in terms of the Constitution.

⁴¹Of the Republic of South African Constitution of 1996.

⁴²Of the Republic of South Africa Constitution of 1996

Furthermore, sub-section (5) of section 199⁴⁴ ‘states that the security service must act, and must teach, and require their members to act, in accordance with the constitution and the law, including customary international law and international agreements binding on the Republic.’

Again, the South Africa interim constitution (Act 200 of 1993)⁴⁵ provided for the establishment of police service in terms of an Act of parliament ‘which shall be structured at both national and provincial levels and shall function under the directives of the national government as well, as the various provincial governments’. Additionally, section 214 of the same provides for the establishment and maintenance of uniform standard of policing at all levels regarding:

- i. The exercise of Police Powers
- ii. The recruitment, appointment, promotion, and transfer member of the service
- iii. Suspension, dismissal, discipline, and grievance procedures
- iv. The training, conduct and conditions of service of members of the service
- v. The general management, control, maintenance, and provision of the service
- vi. Returns, register, records, documents, forms and correspondence...

⁴⁴Ibid.

⁴⁵ Ibid; Mabasa and Olutola, ‘Cogent Social, Science (2021), www document, available at 7:1959974. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2021.1959974>. cited in LC Asogwa (Note 35)

Also section 215 of the Interim Constitution created the powers and functions of the police service as follows:

- i. Prevention of crime, investigation of any offence or alleged offence;
- ii. Maintenance of law and order; and
- iii. Preservation of internal security of the Republic from the provision of these two sections 214 and 215

5. Recommendations

To ensure a robust initiatives of Police powers and control in Nigeria and South Africa, certain measures ought to be taken such as the need for more professional labour force, capacity building programmes and incentives for Police force.

Also, there is a need for more professional labour force in the Nigeria Police. This is because the institution of the police has proliferated into a more advanced one in dealing with civic policing, e-policing, forensic science, auditing and other specialties. Thus, there is need for more manpower with expertise to man those offences. The current employment ratio of Nigeria Police force should be increased

Equally, there is need for constant training and retraining of Police Force in democratic policing. Areas of concern include crowd management e-policing, emotional intelligence and other associated areas. Also, the general welfare of Police Force in these two nation must always be given priority by the National governments of the two countries here.

6. Conclusion

It is a well-known fact that this work ex-rays that both Nigerian and South African

Irish International Journal of Law, Political Sciences and Administration

I. Int. J. L. Pol. Sci. Admin.

Volume: 10; Issue: 01,

January – February, 2026

ISSN: 2146– 3283

Impact Factor: 8.17

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ijlpsa/index>

constitutions provide for a single police system to ensure effective control of crime in the two Nations. No nation can survive effectively of a good policing. It is in line with this that we opine here that should the nations under this discussion should adopt and apply the recommendations stated in this work policing in the two nations would be worthy to be emulated world over.

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